

A STUDY ON EFFECTIVE UTILIZATION OF LIBRARY AMONG STUDENT IN DHANALAKSHMI SRINIVASAN ENGINEERING COLLEGE, PERAMBALUR

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Abstract:

The project report titled a study on effective utilization of library among students in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur. The sample constitutes the students belonging to different departments. The data's were collected from primary sources. Primary data was collected through an administered questionnaire with twenty five questions. Census sampling technique was done to draw the sample size of 240 respondents from the 2268 students. The objectives considered for the study were to the awareness and utilization of DELNET, E-books, E-journals. From the analysis, it is concluded that most of the students are satisfied with the library provided by the institution and they are satisfied with the library material useful for the journal publications.

Key Words: Awareness of Library resource, Effective of Library, Delnet and Publication of Journals.

Introduction:

Education is the key factor in the development and advancement of a society. Each individual in a country should be considered as an asset because it is due to the overall contribution of human resources that a nation can progress and advance. To integrate each individual in the process of development and advancement of the nation, suitable education and training is very important. Since education and training of an individual is a lifelong process every nation must be aware of this fact, if proper directions are to be given to its people. The libraries of these institutions serve a variety of users such as students, faculty, administrators and staff with diverse information needs. These libraries collect a variety of information sources and offer various services for supporting instructional, research and learning activities. Hence, the importance of libraries in academic institutions is considerable and they are often viewed as a nucleus of academic activity.

Review of Literature:

Majid Shaheen & Tan, Ai. Tee (2002), undertook a study entitled “Usage of Information resources by Computer engineering students: a case study of Nan Yang Technological University” they investigated that the use of databases, electronic journals and other electronics information sources was surprisingly low among the computer engineering under graduate students at Nanyang Technological University (NTU), Singapore. The study recommended that more aggressive campaigning is required for creating awareness about electronic information sources.

Carol, Tenopir (2003), in the study entitled “Use and user of Electronic library Resources: an Overview and Analysis of Recent Research studies” analyzed the result of over two hundred studies on the usage of electronic resources in libraries published from 1995 to 2003. Resulted drawn from this study indicate that the electronic resources have been rapidly adopted in academic spheres, though the behavior varies according to the discipline.

Ajayi. N. A & Adetaya, J.O (2005), in their work “Utilization of Library books to Enhance Academic Excellence in Nigeria Tertiary Institution: A case Study of Hexejiah Oluwasanmi library” they have found that the students and staff members have fully utilized the library. There was a progressive increase in the number of printed books borrowed and consultation of library users from 159,134 in 1997-98 sessions to 295,121 in 2000-2001 session. The progressive increase in the utilization of printed books is an indication that the library is meeting its primary role of supporting the objective of its institution.

Ali, Naushad (2005), in the work “The use of Electronic Resources at IIT Delhi Library; a study of search Behaviors” carried out a study on the use of electronic resources by teachers, students and research scholars of universities and research organizations. Seventy eight percent (78%) of the respondents feel that the use of the UGC Infonet e-journals has created high dependency value on their research work and they need current article alert services and electronic document supply services.

Kaur, Baljinder, & Verma, Rama (2006), in their study, “Use of Electronic Resources at TIET library Patiala: A case study”, found that users use all the sources available to them regularly: CD ROMs, online databases, Web resources and Audio/Videotapes.

Syamalamba Rani (2009) carried out a study entitled “Library Use Pattern of Undergraduate Students in Minority Degree Colleges in Andhra Pradesh”. This study, which was conducted in minority aided degree colleges, reveals the nature and the extent of use of college libraries in Andhra Pradesh. It evaluates in detail the type of material, sources and the services used by the students. It also assesses the extent of student’s satisfaction regarding collection, timings and library staff cooperation in finding the information.

Objectives of the Study:

- A study on Effective Utilization of Library among students in Dhanalakshmi Srinivasan Engineering College, Perambalur
- To analyzes the level of awareness of library resource by student.
- To analyze the utilization of DELNET, e-books, e-journals.
- To analyzes the effective utilization of journals for publications.

Research Methodology:

Research is the process of systematic and in depth study or search of any particular topic, subject or area of investigation, backed by collection, compilation, Presentation and interpretation of relevant details or data. It is careful search or find out valuation facts, which would be useful for further application or utilization.

Research Design:

The researcher used Descriptive Research Design. Descriptive Research design means fact finding one. The Research used this research design to find out the fact of respondents attitude and opinion about student empowerment.

Sampling Design:

The Sampling type is Simple Random Sample which involves deliberating selection of particular units constituting a sample, which represents the universe, is used for conducting the study.

Sample Size:

Sample size denotes the number of sample selected for the study. They sample size for this study is fixed at 240 respondents.

Data Collection Method:

Data are the basic input to any decision making processing of data gives statistics of importance of study.

Sources of Data:

- Primary Data

Primary Data:

Primary Data were collected through Questionnaire. The data which are collected a fresh for the first time and happen to be original in character.

Statistical Tools and Techniques:

- Percentage Analysis
- Chi-square test
- Correlation
- ANOVA

Limitation of the Study:

- As opinions are dynamic the results of the study based on these opinions are likely to differ in future.
- The result also depends on the integrity of the respondents in giving true and fair opinions and their level of knowledge in subject under study.
- The study also inherits all the limitations of the sampling technique used for conducting the survey.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Students Awareness of Library Resource

S.No	Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Strongly Agree	54	22.5
2	Agree	152	63.33
3	Neutral	30	12.5
4	Strongly Disagree	4	1.67
5	Disagree	-	-
	Total	240	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference:

The above table shows that, 22.5% of respondents are Strongly Agree with the awareness of library resources, 63.33% of respondents are Agree with the awareness of library resources, 12.5% of respondents are

Neutral with the awareness of library resources, 1.67 % of respondents are Disagree with the awareness of library resources.

Chart:

Students Awareness of Library Resource:

Correlation:

Aware about the library resource (X)	54	152	30	4	0	240
Satisfied with the resource of library (Y)	18	158	44	12	8	240

X	Y	X ²	Y ²	XY
54	18	2916	324	972
152	158	23104	24964	24016
30	44	900	1936	1320
4	12	16	144	48
0	8	0	64	0
$\sum X=240$	$\sum Y=240$	$\sum X^2=29936$	$\sum Y^2=27432$	$\sum XY=26356$

Answer: $r_{xy} = 0.867$

Inference:

There is high positive correlation between Aware about the library resource (X) and Satisfied with the resource of library(Y).

Suggestions:

In order to improve the awareness about the DELNET facility to the students. Only minimum of the students are utilizing library once in a week. So make them to visit daily. Make an curiosity towards the students about latest collection of books are arrival at library. Students have any queries or doubts related to subjects, they started to research at library. Each of the students are utilizing and gaining information to increase their IQ level. Students are easily intimidated when they do not get the response properly so to make them familiar with the resources librarian should be more friendly, co-operative and helpful. Libraries should aim to make all the users aware of the information resources and services available, both directly and through external sources at the library. Teaching staff and library staff should collaborate to ensure that library resources along with electronic resources are appropriately used by the students. Ensure there are sufficient networked computers available for students, especially at peak times. Libraries should also consider the Internet as one of the most important information sources and develop its infrastructure accordingly.

Conclusion:

On the basis of the above observation one can conclude that. Library is an important part of any academic Institution. It is a Universe of knowledge an institution responsible for acquiring or providing information through various primary source or secondary sources made available in various format. It plays a pivotal role in widening the knowledge frontiers which leads to attainment of intellectual heights. It is quite evident that student as a whole use physical libraries to a great extent for study purpose which is proved by the study that they do see their particular library as a part of the educational institution and visits there to inquire about the books that are acquired and for the basic purpose of lending and returning. They are satisfied with the library material which is used for journals.

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